

Determination of Mercaptans by Titration with Potassium Periodate

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A rapid and precise periodatometric determination of mercaptans is described. Samples were titrated in aqueous or dilute acetic acid medium with potassium periodate solution in dilute sulphuric acid. The blue colour with starch serves to detect the end point. Glucose, propylene glycol, acetaldehyde, carbondisulfide and elemental sulfur do not interfere. Thiocarbonyl compounds and sulfocyanide ions interfere.

MERCAPTANS are fairly reactive compounds and several methods have been proposed for their determination. Most of the primary and secondary mercaptans can be determined by titration with standard iodine¹. Amperometric silver titration sometimes gives low results due to the high susceptibility of mercaptans to oxidation in ammonical solution². In indirect determination with excess acrylonitrile³, the reaction time for high mercaptans is as high as 1 hr. Kolthoff, Strikes and Morren⁴ titrated mercaptan in biological substances, with mercuric chloride amperometrically whereas Firtz and Palmer⁵ used mercuric perchlorate for visual titration of mercaptans.

In the present work a procedure has been evolved for direct visual titration of mercaptans in aqueous or dilute acetic acid medium by potassium periodate, mercaptans being oxidised to their corresponding disulfides according to the reaction :

The reaction is immediate and its end point may be indicated by the blue colour of starch.

Reagents :

Potassium periodate solution was prepared by dissolving about 1.6 g of commercially available sample in 250 ml of distilled water containing 10.0 ml of 5*N* sulfuric acid. The undissolved material was filtered off through a sintered glass crucible and the clear filtrate was diluted to 1 litre. The strength of the solution was determined iodometrically.

Mercaptan solutions were prepared by dissolving samples of highest purity available, in distilled water or in glacial acetic acid and their strength determined by titration with standard iodine¹.

Procedure :

2.0 to 20.0 ml of the sample solution containing 2 to 150 mg of mercaptan, were pipetted into a 150 ml. Erlenmeyer flask and 1 ml of 1% starch solution added to it. Water insoluble mercaptan samples were dissolved in glacial acetic acid and to an aliquot of the solution sufficient distilled water was added to keep the acetic acid concentration nearly 30% by volume. This was titrated with standard potassium periodate solution added from a 10 ml microburette to a blue colour.

Results and Discussion

Quantitative results for the determination of several mercaptans are given in Table 1. Most of the primary and secondary mercaptans can be titrated with periodate and no special care is required for getting accurate results.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MERCAPTANS

Mercaptan titrated	Weight (mg)		% Error
	Taken	Found	
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	34.55	34.59	±0.0
	12.95	12.81	-1.1
Thioglycolic acid	27.37	27.33	-0.2
	6.84	6.77	-1.1
Benzyl Mercaptan	83.95	83.95	±0.0
	125.92	127.70	+1.4
Allyl Thiol	46.46	47.12	+0.1
	9.29	9.39	+0.3
Thiobenzoic acid	18.54	18.46	-0.5
	27.81	27.39	-1.5
2-Mercapto ethylamine	32.55	32.49	-0.2
hydrochloride	13.02	12.68	-2.6
2-Diethylaminoethane thiol	14.89	14.73	-1.0
hydrochloride	37.23	36.24	-2.6
2-Mercaptoethanol	3.87	3.86	-0.2
	27.09	27.21	+0.4
p-Chlorotoluene-α-thiol	10.24	10.20	-0.4
	56.20	56.12	-0.1
Methyl-3-mercaptopropionate	8.86	8.90	+0.4
	35.44	35.36	-0.3

TABLE 2—INTERFERENCES

Mercaptan titrated	Substance added	Molar Ratio added compd/ RSH	RSH* % recovery
2-Mercapto-propionic acid	Elemental sulfur	18 : 1	100.2
	Glucose	50 : 1	100.4
	Propylene glycol	35 : 1	100.4
	<i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene	100 : 1	100.2
	Acetaldehyde	29 : 1	100.2
	Methylacrylate	5 : 1	100.5
	Acrylonitrile	158 : 1	100.3
Mercaptoacetic acid	Sodium chloride	25 : 1	99.8
	Potassium bromide	20 : 1	99.6
	Diacetone alcohol	12 : 1	100.3
	Urea	8 : 1	99.8
	Fructose	24 : 1	100.0
	Sulfosalicylic acid	12 : 1	99.8
2-Mercaptoethyl-ammonium chloride	Methylsalicylate	39 : 1	100.0
	Bromobenzene	56 : 1	100.3
	Iso-butylmethyl ketone	15 : 1	99.7
	Carbonylsulfide	40 : 1	100.0
	Glycine	27 : 1	99.9
2-Mercapto-ethanol	Thiophene	10 : 1	100.5
	Diphenyldisulfide	39 : 1	100.0
	Dimethylsulfoxide	58 : 1	100.0
	Diethylsulfide	9 : 1	100.1

* Average of 2 determinations, % recovery taken into account previously determined purity of the sample.

In order to check the sensitivity of the procedure, mercaptans were titrated in presence of various interfering compounds and results are summarised in Table 2. Large interferences are due to thio-carbonyl compounds and sulfoeyanide ions.

The method is inapplicable to mercaptans having free β -carboxyl group due to susceptibility to further oxidation⁶.

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